

(0.337) at harvest, followed by P in leaf at 60 d and in stem at harvest. The indirect effects of P in stem, grain, leaf, and sterile panicles via root were all

positive. An indirect positive effect was found via stem at harvest. The direct and indirect contributions of leaf and sound grain were negative. ■

Manoharsali as checks were field tested at research stations and in field trials in Gerua, Tinsukia, and Suklivoria for 1-6 yr. Trials were laid out at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill. Forty kg N as urea was applied in three splits before planting, at tillering, and at panicle initiation; 20 kg/ha each of P and K were applied in the form of single superphosphate and muriate of potash as basal.

IET6666 showed wide adaptability and stability in grain yield under the agroecological conditions of Assam (Table 2). It flowered in 115-120 d and matured in 145-157 d.

The variety is being evaluated for release as Lakhimi for Assam wet season. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

IET6666, a new high-yielding rice variety for Assam

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IET6666, a long-duration, high-yielding variety evolved from RP31-49-2/Patnai

23 by the Directorate of Rice Research in Hyderabad, is suitable for low-lying fields and cloudy weather conditions during wet season. Its coarse grain and intermediate plant height are preferred by the majority of farmers in Assam.

Agronomic characteristics are given in Table 1.

IET6666, 12 other promising cultivars with similar duration, and Mahsuri and

Table 1. Morphological and physiological characteristics of IET6666 and check variety Manoharsali at Titabar, Assam, India.

Character	IET6666	Manoharsali
Plant height (cm)	118.73	148.53
Duration	145	148
Panicles (no./m ²)	257	242
Filled grains (no./panicle)	103	83
1000-grain weight (g)	23.22	24.55
Total dry matter at flowering (kg/ha)	116.76	146.56
Leaf area index	4.58	5.80
Total chlorophyll content at flowering (mg/g fresh wt)	2.23	3.43
N content in leaf tissues at flowering (%)	2.18	1.23
Solar energy utilization efficiency for dry matter (%)	1.87	0.81
Solar energy utilization for grain yield (%)	0.55	0.25

Table 2. Yields of IET6666 and check varieties at different locations in Assam, India 1978-88.

Year	Location	Yield (t/ha)		
		IET6666	Mahsuri	Manoharsali
1978	Titabar	3.4	2.7	-
	Karimganj	3.0	3.3	-
1979	Titabar	5.2	3.8	-
	Karimganj	2.9	3.9	-
1980	Titabar	5.0	4.5	-
	Karimganj	3.6	3.5	-
1982	Titabar	3.8	-	3.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	1.9
1983	Titabar	3.9	-	2.0
	Karimganj	4.4	-	3.5
1984	Titabar	5.3	-	3.1
1985	Titabar	5.3	-	3.2
1986	Titabar	5.2	-	3.2
1987	Titabar	5.4	-	3.2
1988	Titabar	5.1	-	2.6
1984 on-farm trials	Gerua	6.4	-	5.2
	Tinsukia	5.1	-	4.2
	Suklivoria	3.9	-	4.0

Performance of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 under transplanted rainfed lowland conditions in Nepal

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In Nepal, 88% of the rice area (1.45 million ha in 1988) is in the subtropical climatic region of the Tarai belt (67-250 m altitude), the Inner Tarai region, and equivalent climatic region of river basin areas and valleys up to 900 m altitude.

Table 1. Yields of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 at 4 sites in subtropical Nepal, 1983-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				Mean	Increase over check(%)	Experiment site ^a and time
	Tarahara	Parwanipur	Rampur	Nepalganj			
IR46	4.6	2.6	3.0	3.2	3.4	142	Research stations, 1983-84
Improved check Bindeshori	2.4	2.2	2.0	2.8	2.4	100	
IR46	4.8	2.6	2.4	4.2 ^a	3.5	114	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3.3	2.0	-	3.9	3.1	100	
IR10781	3918	2956	2692	2981	3.1	105	Research stations, 1984-85
Improved check Bindeshori	3562	3001	2512	2897	3.0	100	
IR10781	4840	2818	3750	4150	3.9	127	Farmers' fields, 1985-86
Improved check Masuli	3292	2012	-	3900	3.1	100	

^a Farmer's field result of this location is from Nawal Parasi area. Each location includes the results from various farmers' fields.

Under assured irrigation, two crops of rice are grown during the summer (Feb-Jun) and rainy (Jun-Oct) seasons, with a nonrice winter crop grown Nov-Jan.

More than 75% of the country's ricefields are rainfed, dependent on the monsoon. We are trying to identify high-yielding rice varieties suitable for transplanted rainfed lowland conditions.

IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 have shown consistently better performance over recommended check Bindeshori and popular improved variety Masuli (Mahsuri) in trials for the last 5 yr (Table 1). Yields have averaged more than 3.0 t/

Table 2. General agronomic characters of IR46 and IR10781-143-2-3 under transplanted rainfed lowland conditions in subtropical Nepal.^a

Variety	Heading (DAS)	Maturity (DAS)	Culm length (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Av yield (t/ha)
IR46	108	135	96	229	3.4
IR10781-143-2-3	105	137	92	233	3.5
Masuli (most popular)	119	150	100	231	3.0

^aDAS = days after seeding.

ha under rainfed lowland conditions (the national average rice yield is 2.2 t/ha).

Both entries mature at least 10 d earlier than Masuli in the normal (Jun-Oct) planting season (Table 2), giving enough time for farmers to plant winter

crops such as wheat, winter maize, or winter legumes. They are resistant to major diseases bacterial blight and blast. They are being distributed to farmers through the rice minikit program. ■

Seed technology

Using electrical conductivity to determine maturity stage for quality rice seeds

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We studied the influence of maturity stage on the keeping quality of seeds. IR50 grown during 1985 wet season was harvested at 27, 34, and 41 d after 50% anthesis. Seeds were dried to 8% moisture content, treated with captan (N-trichloro methyl thio)-Cyclohex-4-ene-1,2-dicarboximide), and stored in cotton and paper-aluminum foil-polythene laminated (P-AF-P) containers for 9 mo.

Electrical conductivity of the seed leachate was measured at 3-mo intervals using Elico CM-82 Conductivity bridge.

Leachate was prepared using 50 randomly selected seeds, soaked in 50 ml of deionized water for 24 h at room temperature, with two replications.

Harvesting 27 d after 50% anthesis gave the lowest electrical conductivity and highest germination (see table). Harvesting 41 d after 50% flowering gave the highest electrical conductivity and lowest germination. Seeds stored in cotton cloth bags deteriorated more than those stored in P-

AF-P bags, and had higher electrical conductivity. The interaction was significant.

The increased electrical conductivity of seeds harvested 41 d after 50% anthesis in storage showed that they are less vigorous and deteriorate faster than seeds harvested 27 d after 50% anthesis. ■

Electrical conductivity of IR50 seeds stored for 9 months. National Pulses Research Centre, Vamban, India, 1985 wet season.

Harvest date (d after 50% anthesis)		Electrical conductivity ^a (dS/m)								Mean	Germination (%)
		At harvest		3 mo after harvest		6 mo after harvest		9 mo after harvest			
		C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2		
27	Untreated	36.85	36.83	37.61	37.12	39.62	37.18	40.20	37.25	37.83	93
	Treated	36.83	36.83	37.26	37.10	39.80	37.16	40.18	37.20	37.80	96
34	Untreated	39.41	39.41	40.68	39.86	41.86	40.75	44.86	41.86	41.08	92
	Treated	39.41	39.41	41.61	39.68	42.12	39.86	43.86	40.28	40.78	95
41	Untreated	48.64	48.64	53.63	49.24	55.32	51.24	61.23	51.83	52.47	89
	Treated	48.64	48.64	50.24	49.07	54.83	50.61	60.20	51.61	51.73	90
Mean		41.63	41.63	43.51	42.01	45.59	42.80	48.42	43.34		
Germination(%)		94	94	91	94	90	90	89	94		
LSD (0.01)		0.63	0.59	0.39	0.39	0.55	0.39	0.38	0.45	0.45	0.32

^aC1 = cotton bags, C2 = P-AF-P containers.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Mid-storage correction to prolong viability of rice seeds

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We stored seeds of rice cultivars ADT36, Bhavani, and CO 40 at 8.5% moisture content in cloth bags under ambient

conditions. After 8 mo, half the seeds were soaked in double their volume of a dilute sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution (10⁻⁴M) for 6 h, sun-dried to 8.5%, and re-stored for 24 mo.

Hydrated seeds maintained high germination and vigor (in terms of root length) (see table). Nonhydrated seeds lost vigor and viability. Medium-duration cultivar Bhavani had lower storage potential than CO 40 and ADT36. ■